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Nanoparticle based receptor targeted biosensor

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Introduction: Receptor targeted biosensors development is a new concept. Receptors are protein molecules present in the plasma membrane of a living cell which bind to the ligands that receive and transduce signals that may be integrated into biological processes (1). The term sensor, however, sometimes applied to the molecules that only change their location in the cell are either accumulated or released from a specific compartment of a cell or undergo a conformational change caused by a covalent modification triggered by the physiological phenomenon (2). Different membrane protein-based biosensors are suggested by different groups of researchers. Ligand based biosensor has more efficacy than traditional biosensor because ligand has affinity to some selective protein and the binding of ligand receptor has electrochemical sharing. Biological membrane of living cell contains different receptors and so, receptor targeted ligand-based biosensor can perform the sensor functions accurately.

Methods: The literature survey was conducted on published research articles on different receptor-based biosensor and their applications. The selection criteria of the articles are those published the period in between 2015 to 2020. Those articles are studied which are published in Scopus indexed journal and conference proceedings.

Results & Discussions: Different neurotransmitters are conjugated with nanoparticles and the conjugates are attached with some fluorescence molecules. The signals received from the conjugates showed different characteristics after bindings with the ligands. Based on signal characteristics the attached receptors can be identified. Besides, receptor proteins present in some biological membrane shows conformational changes after binding with the ligands and allow the movement of ions through the channels. The ions passing through the channel protein binds with the ligands and then release some electric current which can be measured. These techniques can help in the identification of some biomolecules (3). One of the neurotransmitter-based sensors applied to detect and identification of neurotoxins by using specific enzyme. The probe which is a synaptic protein is cleaved by neurotoxin. So, the quantitative estimation of the neurotransmitter can indicate the neurotoxin level. Aptamer based biosensor technology also suggested to detect different chemicals in the biological system. Probes after binding with the ligand results in a change of the sensor molecule itself that in turn causes a modification of its excitation or emission intensity or both. The changes in the indicator molecule might be either due to conformational change or in electronic distribution. In case of protein-based biosensor, there is a conformational change in the indicator molecule after binding with the ligand while in organic dyes the changes are in electronic distribution.

Conclusions: Based on the studies, it can be concluded that surface charge of the nanoparticles can be modified and conjugated with different opposite charged fluorescence chemicals. This nano conjugate can be attached with the different ligands and the ligand attached conjugate can be used as a binder and activates the receptor molecules. The signal received from the fluoro-probe can be measured both qualitatively and quantitatively.

Keywords: Receptor, Ligand, Nanoparticle, Biosensor

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